

BENEFITS AND DRAWBACKS OF TEACHING BY DIVIDING STUDENT INTO SMALL GROUPS

Qilicheva Makhbuba Aliaskar qizi

Urgench State University

Linguistics: 2nd year graduate student, majoring in English

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Abstract: This article provides an overview of small group learning and teaching, describes the characteristics of this form of small group work, benefits, problems, potential causes of less than optimal sessions, and summarises specific approaches.

Key words: language acquisition, teamwork skill, teacher - student interaction, group work

According to Hall and Hewings, language acquisition is a process that involves interaction between students, teachers, texts, and activities. Nonetheless, Ellis came to the conclusion from earlier research that student-student interaction is more successful than teacher-student interaction in assisting learners to acquire L2. Additionally, Richards argued that groups enable students to engage in more negotiating since the more informal setting allows them to do so without feeling under pressure. GW's promotion of language fluency is one of its key objectives. GW is a technique used in language classrooms that helps students to interact with other students and discuss difficulties in a less intimidating setting.

Grouping is regarded as an effective teaching strategy, particularly in EFL classes, for a number of reasons, including the maximization of the amount of time that students can speak the target language. In addition, it cuts down on the amount of time that students spend watching other students interact with the teacher; additionally, it eliminates the anxiety that prevents some language learners from speaking and interacting with the teacher in front of the entire class; and finally, it gives the teacher more chances to go over the task's structure with students.

Students may be more independent in groups since they are encouraged to share their knowledge and learn from others. In contrast, because the teacher is doing most of the talking in teacher-fronted situations, students could be more reliant.

According to several researches (Brown, 2001; Foster, 1998; Ghaith & Yaghi, 1998; Harmer, 1991), GW is effective in language courses because it allows students to practice their English with other group members. Group work also maximizes the advantages for pupils in the classroom. In particular, it can be utilized to enhance oral exercises for language learners, finish tasks that call for group discussion, exchange reading and listening activities, and collaborate on writing. It also offers the significant benefit of enabling various student groups to carry out various duties and activities in accordance with their aptitude.

McDonough investigated how instructors and students felt about the usage of pair and small-group activities in a Thai EFL environment and looked at whether the learning possibilities associated with these activities actually took place in a classroom setting. Also, he looked into whether participants in the pair and small-group exercises produced the goal forms more effectively. The findings showed that learners who participated more in the pair and small-

group activities produced the target forms more effectively, even if they did not think the activities were helpful for their learning.

New perspective.

There is some truth to the adage "two heads are better than one." Researchers discovered that when students may collaborate, for instance on a problem-solving activity, they are more inclined to try out several approaches to the problem. Positive and negative comments can help them learn more quickly.

Also, students learn better when they debate and challenge one another's viewpoints and justifications since this enables them to create a variety of approaches to complete a task. According to research, doing this encourages cognitive reorganization, which improves academic, social, and emotional learning.

Personal satisfaction.

Working in a group is not always easy. However, achieving a decent score may be incredibly fulfilling and motivating when students are able to overcome all the tension, stress, and long hours that come with group assignments.

According to research, students who participate in group discussions and work on the given problem-solving activity are very committed to finding a solution. Students who were more involved in the solution-finding process express greater levels of satisfaction with their contribution to the choice than those who weren't. This results in a more favorable portrayal of their collective learning experience.

Teamwork skills.

Students can investigate complex tasks that they normally wouldn't have done if they were working alone thanks to teamwork, which improves both their individual and group learning. This is so that they can experience different viewpoints, modes of thought, and dispute while working in groups.

This offers pupils the chance to develop their communication and teamwork abilities, as well as a greater capacity for idea generation. This supports a more all-encompassing approach to learning and can boost group productivity.

The majority of students said that they enjoyed working in groups because it allowed them to benefit from peer assistance. It was difficult, according to learners, to ask the teacher to make clear any doubts or queries they had. Hence, it seems that language learners preferred to ask other group members to clarify specific concerns for them, possibly as a result of a relatively formal interaction between language learners and their teachers. Also, students said that when other group members responded to their inquiries, they were better able to understand an explanation.

Students also believed that individuals in a group have various experiences and expertise to impart. For instance, students clarified that asking for assistance from group members may lead to more rapid learning.

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